

Quinazolones. Part III

Synthesis of Some Angular α -Pyronoquinazolones

S. K. P. Sinha

The one step synthesis of 7-methoxy-2-methyl/phenyl-4'-methyl-3-phenyl- α -pyrono(5',6' : 5,6)-quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (III) and (IV) from the respective hydroxyquinazolones (I) and (II) have been described.

Our interest¹ on the synthesis of condensed quinazolones having a heterocyclic ring fused in the phenyl part of the quinazolone moiety prompted us to undertake the synthesis of some angular α -pyronoquinazolones which have not so far been reported in the literature. The present communication deals with the synthesis of such α -pyronoquinazolones : 7-methoxy-2,4'-dimethyl-3-phenyl- α -pyrono-(5',6' : 5,6) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) and its 2-phenyl analogue (IV).

Out of the two possible ways to obtain α -pyronoquinazolones : (i) developing an α -pyrone ring over a quinazolone nucleus and (ii) building a pyrimidone ring over a coumarin nucleus, the first procedure, adopted to prepare these compounds, is described in this paper. Adaptation of this procedure required the application of Pechmann reaction on a preformed hydroxyquinazolone. Accordingly, for developing an α -pyrone ring at the 5,6-position of a preformed quinazolone moiety, 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I)² and 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II)³ were considered to be the suitable starting materials. The presence of a methoxyl group at C₍₇₎ was with a view to block the alternative ortho position which may be involved during cyclodehydration.

I : R = CH₃
II : R = Ph

III : R = CH₃
IV : R = Ph

The synthetic sequence outlined has been realised and condensation of I and II with ethyl aceto acetate in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid gave the respective α -pyronoquinazolones : 7-methoxy-2,4'-dimethyl-3-phenyl- α -pyrono (5',6' : 5,6) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) and 7-methoxy-4'-methyl-2,3-diphenyl- α -pyrono (5',6' : 5,6) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV).

1. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 31 and subsequent papers.
2. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 926
3. S. K. P. Sinha Proceedings paper, Part I,

The α -pyrono structure of the compounds are proved by elemental analysis as well as intense IR absorption bands at 1667 cm^{-1} , 1602 cm^{-1} and 1720 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of both α -pyrone and quinazolone rings.

All attempts to prepare the isomeric linear α -pyronoquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI), however failed as 7-hydroxyquinazolones (V)⁴ did not undergo Pechmann condensation probably due to the protonation of the nitrogen at position 1 which would diminish the nucleophilic potential at position 6.

EXPERIMENTAL*

7-Methoxy-2,4'-dimethyl-3-phenyl- α -pyrono (5',6' : 5,6) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) : I (2.82 g.; 0.01 mole) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.; 0.01 mole) were mixed and cooled in an ice bath. The cold reaction mixture was then gradually added to well cooled concentrated sulphuric acid (29.4 g.; 0.03 mole) and left overnight. The solution thus obtained was poured in crushed ice, the solid that separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give III as colourless needles (2.4 g.; 70%), m.p. $275\text{--}276^\circ$. (Found : C, 70.2; H, 4.8; N, 8.2. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 68.9; H, 4.6; N, 8.0%). IR (KBr) 1500 cm^{-1} , 1602 cm^{-1} (quinazolone), 1667 cm^{-1} (α -pyrone), 1720 cm^{-1} (quinazolone) and UV λ_{max} (EtOH) $243\text{ m}\mu$ (E, 33396).

7-Methoxy-4'-methyl-2,3-diphenyl- α -pyrono (5',6' : 5,6) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV) : II (3.44 g.; 0.01 mole) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 g.; 0.01 mole) were mixed and cooled in an ice bath. The cold mixture when gradually added to well cooled concentrated sulphuric acid (29.4 g.; 0.03 mole) and worked up as in the previous case gave colourless solid. It was crystallised from ethanol to furnish IV as elongated needles (2 g.; 50%), m.p. $212\text{--}213^\circ$ (d). (Found : C, 72.8; H, 4.5; N, 7.0. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 73.1; H, 4.4; N, 6.8%). IR (KBr) 1600 cm^{-1} (quinazolone), 1667 cm^{-1} (α -pyrone), 1720 cm^{-1} (quinazolone) and UV λ_{max} (EtOH) $245\text{ m}\mu$ (E, 34842).

Chemistry Laboratory,
L. S. College,
Bihar University,
Muzaffarpur, (Bihar).

Received September 7, 1970

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

4. S. K. P. Sinha, P. K. Banerjee and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1089